

Structural aspects and physico-chemical properties of some aromatic polar nitro compounds in solvent benzene at different temperatures under Giga Hertz electric field

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Manuscript received 14 September 2005, revised 22 March 2006, accepted 4 April 2006

Abstract : An interesting method based on complex orientational susceptibilities χ_{ij}^* s to study the dielectric relaxation mechanism of some standard polar nitro compounds in nonpolar solvent benzene has been prescribed and applied successfully to arrive at their structural and physico-chemical properties. The dielectric orientational susceptibilities χ_{ij} , the real and χ_{ij}'' , the imaginary part of χ_{ij}^* are involved with the measured relative permittivities ϵ'_{ij} and ϵ''_{ij} of ϵ_{ij}^* of Pant *et al.* to measure the relaxation time τ_j of all the polar solutes from the ratio of the linear coefficients of individual variations of χ_{ij}'' and χ_{ij} with weight fraction w_j 's of the respective solute. They are further compared with τ_j 's obtained from the direct slope of the linear variations of χ_{ij}'' and χ_{ij} and Gopala Krishna's method measured by Pant *et al.* The temperature variation of τ_j 's from the former method helps one get the thermodynamic energy parameters i.e. enthalpy of activation ΔH_τ , entropy of activation ΔS_τ , and free energy of activation ΔF_τ of dielectric relaxation by using the rate process equation of Eyring *et al.*, to throw much light on their structural and physico-chemical properties. The dimensionless parameter δ ($= \Delta H_\tau / \Delta H \eta_\tau$) which is the slope of the linear equation of $\ln \tau_j T = \ln a + \delta \ln \eta_j$, where η_j is the coefficient of viscosity of the solvent, is used to get Debye and Kalman factors. They reflect the associative nature along with the applicability of Debye-Smyth model of dielectric relaxation for such polar nitro molecules. The estimated dipole moments μ_j 's in terms of linear coefficient β 's of χ_{ij}'' vs w_j like $\chi_{ij}'' = \alpha + \beta w_j + \gamma w_j^2$ curves and dimensionless parameters b 's involved with measured τ_j 's are finally compared with theoretical dipole moments μ_{theo} 's, obtained from available bond angles and bond moments of the substituent polar groups of the molecules as well as with μ_j 's of Gopala Krishna's method used by Pant *et al.* to shed more light on the conformations of the molecules, in addition to inductive, mesomeric and electromeric effects.

Keywords : Structural aspects, nitro compounds, Giga Hertz electric field.

The dielectric relaxation mechanism of polar liquid molecules in nonpolar solvents is of much importance as it provides an useful and essential tool to study their structural aspects and physico-chemical properties. The method is involved with estimation of several dielectric relaxation parameters such as relaxation time τ_j , dipole moments μ_j , μ_{theo} and thermodynamic energy parameters. There exists several methods^{1,2} for estimation of relaxation parameters, but all these methods are not so simple like our present one based on susceptibility measurement. Their method^{1,2} consist of placing ϵ''_{ij} against ϵ'_{ij} measured at different frequencies of GHz range to get semicircular plot which cuts ϵ' -axis in the lower and higher points giving rise ϵ_{oi} and ϵ_{oo} respectively. Migahed *et al.*³ and Nandi *et al.*⁴ used the method of thermally stimulated depolarisation current density (TSDC) in terms of *hf* relative permittivities to study

the relaxation mechanism of some polar liquids and the physico-chemical properties of some proteins, polymers, micelles etc. Although several workers^{3,4} studied the relaxation mechanism of polar liquid molecules in nonpolar solvent in terms of measured relative permittivities of ϵ_{ij}^* , the real part and ϵ_{ij}'' , the imaginary part of high frequency (*hf*) complex permittivity ϵ_{ij}^* , but no such investigation on polar nitro compounds by susceptibility measurement has yet been made. The method includes the estimation of real χ_{ij}' ($= \epsilon'_{ij} - \epsilon_{\text{oi}}$) and imaginary χ_{ij}'' ($= \epsilon_{ij}''$) parts of high frequency (*hf*) complex dimensionless dielectric orientational susceptibility χ_{ij}^* at different experimental temperatures in °C under a Giga Hertz electric field from the measured permittivities of ϵ'_{ij} and ϵ''_{ij} of Pant *et al.*⁵. χ_{ij} 's are involved only with the molecular orientational polarisation and the evaluation of accurate relaxation parameters are made pos-

Table 1. Measured τ_j 's from ratio of slopes of individual variations of χ'_{ij} and χ''_{ij} with w_j , relaxation time τ_j from Murthy *et al.*, reported τ_j all are in pico second, correlation coefficient and % of error of $\chi'_{ij} - w_j$ and $\chi''_{ij} - w_j$ curves of Figs 2 and 3, of aromatic polar nitro compounds in nonpolar solvent C_6H_6 at different experimental temperatures in $^{\circ}C$ under 9.58 GHz electric field frequency

Sl no	Systems	Temp ($^{\circ}C$)	Individual slope of variation		Slope of χ''_{ij} vs χ'_{ij} (eq (4))	Ratio of slope of ind variation	Correlation coeff (r) of $\chi'_{ij} - w_j$ and $\chi''_{ij} - w_j$ curves	% of errors of $\chi'_{ij} - w_j$ and $\chi''_{ij} - w_j$ curves	τ_j in psec (eq (4))	τ_j in psec (eq (5))	Reported τ_j in psec of Pant <i>et al.</i> ⁵
			Slope of χ'_{ij} vs w_j at $w_j \rightarrow 0$	Slope of χ''_{ij} vs w_j at $w_j \rightarrow 0$							
1	2,5-Dichloro-nitrobenzene	20	24.73	16.36	0.66	0.68	0.98	1.04	10.98	10.98	10.01
		30	77.03	45.93	0.60	0.60	0.92	4.81	9.90	9.90	9.43
		40	78.54	46.01	0.59	0.59	0.90	5.76	9.72	9.72	6.64
2	3,5-Dichloro-nitrobenzene	20	27.35	21.10	0.77	0.77	0.96	2.55	12.81	12.81	11.95
		30	131.44	88.76	0.68	0.68	0.91	5.05	11.21	11.21	8.20
		40	39.69	20.04	0.50	0.50	0.99	0.71	8.38	8.38	7.48
3	2,5-Dibromo-nitrobenzene	20	91.74	135.29	1.47	1.47	0.96	2.13	24.48	24.48	21.50
		30	3.40	4.63	1.36	1.36	0.99	0.87	22.62	22.62	19.63
		40	29.92	39.28	1.31	1.31	0.98	1.15	21.79	21.79	19.19
4	2,4-Dinitro-chlorobenzene	20	5.23	5.36	1.02	1.02	0.98	1.48	17.00	17.00	15.24
		30	25.42	23.24	0.91	0.91	0.89	6.45	15.18	15.17	14.32
		40	20.00	14.47	0.72	0.72	0.94	3.56	12.01	12.01	11.21
5	3,4-Dinitro-chlorobenzene	20	1.29	1.37	1.06	1.06	0.97	1.78	17.60	17.60	15.83
		30	9.59	8.24	0.86	0.86	0.96	2.44	14.25	14.25	13.01
		40	0.23	0.16	0.71	0.71	0.96	2.52	11.82	11.82	10.12

Table 2. The coefficients of α , β , γ of $\chi'_{ij} - w_j$ curves of Fig 3, dimensionless parameters b 's with τ_j of eq (8), measured dipole moment μ_j , reported dipole moment μ_j (Gopala Krishna), theoretical dipole moments μ_j in coulomb metre (C m) of some aromatic polar liquids in benzene at various experimental temperatures in $^{\circ}C$ under 9.58 GHz electric field frequency

Sl no	Systems (Molecular weight, M_j)	Temp ($^{\circ}C$)	$\chi'_{ij} = \alpha + \beta w_j + \gamma w_j^2$			Dimensionless parameter $b = 1/(1 + \omega^2 \tau_j^2)$	Measured $\mu_j \times 10^{30}$ (C m)	$\mu_j \times 10^{30}$ in C m (Pant <i>et al.</i>)	$\mu_j(\text{theo}) \times 10^{30}$ in C m from bond moments
			α	β	γ				
1	2,5-Dichloro-nitrobenzene ($M_j = 0.1920$ kg)	20	-284.43	24.727	-0.35	0.696	26.18	15.19	
		30	-1223.1	77.025	-1.06	0.738	45.99	15.44	14.17
		40	-1262.6	78.537	-1.07	0.745	47.33	14.82	
2	3,5-Dichloro-nitrobenzene ($M_j = 0.1920$ kg)	20	-404.56	27.352	-0.36	0.627	29.01	8.87	
		30	-1978.7	131.44	-1.94	0.687	62.27	16.41	14.17
		40	-448.35	39.688	-0.69	0.797	32.52	17.06	
3	2,5-Dibromo-nitrobenzene ($M_j = 0.2810$ kg)	20	-1456.2	91.74	-1.3	0.315	90.66	34.33	
		30	203.44	3.3988	-0.13	0.350	16.97	30.99	14.17
		40	-323.28	29.92	-0.46	0.367	50.33	30.81	
4	2,4-Dinitro-chlorobenzene ($M_j = 0.2025$ kg)	20	37.556	5.2318	-0.15	0.488	14.77	17.74	
		30	-264.67	25.42	-0.47	0.545	31.58	12.37	12.36
		40	-186.98	20.003	-0.36	0.656	26.12	12.59	
5	3,4-Dinitro-chlorobenzene ($M_j = 0.2025$ kg)	20	191.45	1.2885	0.019	0.471	7.46	17.76	
		30	-147.89	9.5948	-0.01	0.576	18.87	12.37	25.18
		40	199.23	0.2286	0.068	0.663	2.78	14.69	

sible. It is evident from Fig. 1 that the variation of χ''_{ij} with χ'_{ij} is strictly linear, the slope of which presented in Table 1, is used to get τ_j 's of the polar solutes. Murthy *et al.*⁶, however, showed earlier that a similar linear relationship exists between hf imaginary part $K''_{ij}(w_j)$ and real part $K'_{ij}(w_j)$ of complex conductivity $K^*_{ij}(w_j)$ from which τ_j for polar molecules could be estimated. But for associative liq-

uids in the higher concentration the variation of χ''_{ij} and χ'_{ij} is not always linear⁷, the ratio of the linear coefficients of individual polynomial variation of both χ'_{ij} and χ''_{ij} with weight fractions w_j 's like $\chi'_{ij} = \alpha + \beta w_j + \gamma w_j^2$ of solutions⁸ as displayed in Figs. 2 and 3, may be a better choice⁹ to estimate τ_j 's of polar liquid compounds τ_j 's so estimated, are presented in Table 1 for comparison with τ_j 's (11th col-

Table 3. The thermodynamic energy parameters : enthalpy of activation ΔH_{τ} , entropy of activation ΔS_{τ} and free energy of activation ΔF_{τ} , measured by our method (a) and measured by Pant *et al.* (b), value of δ from equation $\ln \tau_j T = \ln a + \delta \ln \eta_j$, enthalpy of activation ΔH_{η_j} due to viscous flow of solvent, Debye factor and Kalman factor of some aromatic polar liquids in benzene at various experimental temperatures in $^{\circ}\text{C}$ under 9.58 GHz electric field frequency

Sl. no.	System	Temp. ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	ΔH_{τ} (kJ mol $^{-1}$)		ΔS_{τ} (J mol $^{-1}$)		ΔF_{τ} (kJ mol $^{-1}$)		Value of δ	$\Delta H_{\eta_j} = (\Delta H_{\tau}/\delta)$ (kJ mol $^{-1}$)	Debye factor $(\tau_j T/\eta_j) \times 10^6$	Kalman factor $(\tau_j T/\eta_j)^{\delta}$
			a	b	a	b	a	b				
			1.	2,5-Dichloronitrobenzene	20	2.16	13.00	-0.0277				
		30	2.16	13.00	-0.0274	0.0088	10.45	10.33	0.04	5.99	5.35	4.45×10^{-8}
		40	2.16	13.00	-0.0277	0.0101	10.83	9.84	0.36	5.99	5.82	4.63×10^{-8}
2.	3,5-Dichloronitrobenzene	20	13.58	15.44	0.0100	0.0169	10.65	10.49	2.10	6.46	6.08	2.09×10^{-2}
		30	13.58	15.44	0.0093	0.0181	10.77	9.97	2.10	6.46	6.05	2.30×10^{-2}
		40	13.58	15.44	0.0100	0.0169	10.45	10.15	2.10	6.46	5.02	2.07×10^{-2}
3.	2,5-Dibromonitrobenzene	20	1.93	1.86	-0.0352	-0.0343	12.24	11.92	0.31	6.15	11.62	7.26×10^{-8}
		30	1.93	1.86	-0.0350	-0.0341	12.54	12.18	0.31	6.15	12.22	7.15×10^{-8}
		40	1.93	1.86	-0.0352	-0.0344	12.94	12.61	0.31	6.15	13.04	7.27×10^{-8}
4.	2,4-Dinitrochlorobenzene	20	10.69	9.12	-0.0023	-0.0067	11.35	11.08	1.65	6.46	8.07	1.02×10^{-3}
		30	10.69	9.12	-0.0028	-0.0075	11.53	11.38	1.65	6.46	8.20	1.10×10^{-3}
		40	10.69	9.12	-0.0022	-0.0067	11.39	11.21	1.65	6.46	7.19	1.01×10^{-3}
5.	3,4-Dinitrochlorobenzene	20	12.67	14.50	0.0042	0.0114	11.43	11.17	2.00	6.33	8.36	1.37×10^{-2}
		30	12.67	14.50	0.0043	0.0111	11.37	11.14	2.00	6.33	7.69	1.39×10^{-2}
		40	12.67	14.50	0.0042	0.0114	11.34	10.94	2.00	6.33	7.07	1.37×10^{-2}

Fig. 1. Variation of imaginary part χ''_{ij} of hf orientational susceptibility against real part χ'_{ij} of hf orientation susceptibility of some polar nitro compounds in nonpolar solvent benzene at different temperatures in $^{\circ}\text{C}$ under 9.5846 GHz electric field frequency of 2,5-dichloronitrobenzene [Ia at 20 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (○), Ib at 30 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (◊), Ic at 40 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (◻)], 3,5-dichloronitrobenzene [IIa at 20 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (■), IIb at 30 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (Δ), IIc at 40 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (▲)], 2,5-dibromonitrobenzene [IIIa at 20 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (○), IIIb at 30 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (◊), IIIc at 40 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (◻)], 2,4-dinitrochlorobenzene [IVa at 20 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (*), IVb at 30 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (-), IVc at 40 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (+)], 3,4-dinitrochlorobenzene [Va at 20 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (Δ), Vb at 30 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (◻), Vc at 40 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (○)].

Fig. 2. Variation of imaginary part χ''_{ij} of hf orientational susceptibility against weight fraction w_j of some polar nitro compounds in nonpolar solvent benzene at different temperatures in $^{\circ}\text{C}$ under 9.5846 GHz electric field frequency of 2,5-dichloronitrobenzene [Ia at 20 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (○), Ib at 30 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (◊), Ic at 40 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (◻)], 3,5-dichloronitrobenzene [IIa at 20 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (■), IIb at 30 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (Δ), IIc at 40 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (▲)], 2,5-dibromonitrobenzene [IIIa at 20 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (○), IIIb at 30 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (◊), IIIc at 40 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (◻)], 2,4-dinitrochlorobenzene [IVa at 20 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (*), IVb at 30 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (-), IVc at 40 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (+)], 3,4-dinitrochlorobenzene [Va at 20 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (Δ), Vb at 30 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (◻), Vc at 40 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (○)].

umn) calculated by Pant *et al.*⁵ by using Gopala Krishna's method¹⁰. The excellent agreement of τ_j 's by both of our

prescribed methods in case of polar nitro compounds which includes the names of 2,5-dichloronitrobenzene, 3,5-dichloronitrobenzene, 2,5-dibromonitrobenzene, 2,4-dinitro-

Fig. 3. Variation of real part χ''_{ij} of *hf* orientational susceptibility against weight fraction w_j of some polar nitro compounds in nonpolar solvent benzene at different temperatures in °C under 9.5846 GHz electric field frequency of 2,5-dichloronitrobenzene [Ia at 20 °C (○), Ib at 30 °C (◐), Ic at 40 °C (◑)], 3,5-dichloronitrobenzene [IIa at 20 °C (■), IIb at 30 °C (Δ), IIc at 40 °C (▲)], 2,5-dibromonitrobenzene [IIIa at 20 °C (○), IIIb at 30 °C (◐), IIIc at 40 °C (◑)], 2,4-dinitrochlorobenzene [IVa at 20 °C (*), IVb at 30 °C (-), IVc at 40 °C (+)], 3,4-dinitrochlorobenzene [Va at 20 °C (Δ), Vb at 30 °C (◐), Vc at 40 °C (O)].

chlorobenzene, 3,4-dinitrochlorobenzene indicates that the data of $\chi''_{ij}(w_j)$ and $\chi'_{ij}(w_j)$ are of low weight fractions w_j 's so that the polar-polar interactions are almost eliminated. The estimated τ_j 's involved with dimensionless parameter b 's are now used to obtain *hf* dipole moment μ_j in terms of linear coefficients β 's of curves of $\chi''_{ij} - w_j$ of Fig. 2 using Debye's relation¹¹. The dimensionless parameter b 's, linear coefficients β 's and estimated μ_j 's are placed in Table 2 to compare with μ_j 's by Gopala Krishna's method¹⁰ measured by Pant *et al.*⁵ and theoretical dipole moments μ_{theo} 's of Fig. 4, evaluated by vector addition of available bond moments of the substituent polar groups of the nitro compounds as seen in Table 2. The disagreement between estimated μ_j and μ_{theo} shows the probable existence of inductive, mesomeric and electromeric effects¹² suffered by the polar groups under the electric field of GHz frequency. μ_j 's thus measured when plotted against t °C shows convex and concave shapes as seen in Fig. 5, which reflects the stability or instability of the polar-nonpolar liquid mixtures observed elsewhere¹³. The eq. (10) is a linear equation $\ln \tau_j T$ against $1/T$ of Fig. 6. The slope and intercept are used to measure the required thermodynamic energy parameters. ΔH_τ , ΔS_τ and ΔF_τ as placed in Table 3. The parameters so estimated provides a deep insight into the physico-chemical properties¹⁴ of the solute molecules in solvent benzene under GHz electric field. The Debye and Kalman factors as seen in Table 3 shows Debye relaxation mechanism obeyed by the molecules.

Fig. 4. Theoretical dipole moment μ_{theo} ($\times 10^{30}$) in coulomb metre (C.m.) from available bond angle and bond moments of (I) 2,5-dichloronitrobenzene, (II) 3,5-dichloronitrobenzene, (III) 2,5-dibromonitrobenzene, (IV) 2,4-dinitrochlorobenzene, (V) 3,4-dinitrochlorobenzene.

Theoretical formulations :

If $\epsilon''_{\alpha ij}$ be subtracted from ϵ''_{ij} the susceptibility contains only the orientational polarisation¹⁵ and thus the fast polarisation is avoided unlike the ϵ''_{ij} . In absence of reliable measured values of infinitely *hf* and low frequency (*lf*) permittivities $\epsilon_{\alpha ij}$ and ϵ_{oij} , the following Debye-Pallate's equations¹⁶ may safely be used from the measured values of the real ϵ'_{ij} and imaginary ϵ''_{ij} parts of the *hf* complex ϵ_{ij}^* of Pant *et al.*⁵

$$\epsilon'_{ij} = \epsilon_{\alpha ij} + \frac{\epsilon_{oij} - \epsilon_{\alpha ij}}{1 + \omega^2 \tau_j^2} \quad (1)$$

and

$$\epsilon''_{ij} = \frac{\epsilon_{oij} - \epsilon_{\alpha ij}}{1 + \omega^2 \tau_j^2} \omega \tau_j \quad (2)$$

χ''_{ij} and χ'_{ij} 's of functions of w_j 's are well displayed in Figs. 3 and 2 respectively. Both ϵ'_{ij} and ϵ''_{ij} parts of ϵ_{ij}^* are related by¹¹

$$\epsilon'_{ij} = \epsilon_{\alpha ij} + \frac{1}{\omega \tau_j} \epsilon''_{ij} \quad (3)$$

In terms of real χ'_{ij} and imaginary χ''_{ij} parts of *hf* complex susceptibility χ_{ij}^* , one obtains

$$\chi''_{ij} = (\omega \tau_j) \chi'_{ij} \text{ or } d\chi''_{ij} / d\chi'_{ij} = \omega \tau_j \quad (4)$$

Murthy *et al.*⁶ showed earlier that a similar linear relationship exists between *hf* conductivity $K''_{ij}(w_j)$ and $K'_{ij}(w_j)$ from

Fig. 5. Variation of dipole moment μ_j against temperature t in $^{\circ}\text{C}$ of some polar nitro compounds in nonpolar solvent benzene under 9.5846 GHz electric field frequency of (I) 2,5-dichloronitrobenzene ($\square$), (II) 3,5-dichloronitrobenzene (Δ), (III) 2,5-dibromonitrobenzene ($\blacktriangle$), (IV) 2,4-dinitrochlorobenzene ($\circ$), (V) 3,4-dinitrochlorobenzene ($\bullet$).

Fig. 6. Variation of $\ln(\tau_j T)$ against $1/T$ of some polar nitro compounds in nonpolar solvent benzene under 9.5846 GHz electric field frequency of (I) 2,5-dichloronitrobenzene ($\square$), (II) 3,5-dichloronitrobenzene (Δ), (III) 2,5-dibromonitrobenzene ($\blacktriangle$), (IV) 2,4-dinitrochlorobenzene ($\circ$), (V) 3,4-dinitrochlorobenzene ($\bullet$).

which they estimated the relaxation time for polar molecules. The eqs. (4) is a straight line between χ''_{ij} and χ'_{ij} observed graphically in Fig. 1, the slope of which is used to get τ_j of a polar solute⁶ as seen in Table 1. But for most of the associative liquids, the variation of χ''_{ij} against χ'_{ij} is not strictly linear⁹. For such associative polar-nonpolar liquid mixture χ'_{ij} is related with w_j by $\chi'_{ij} = \alpha + \beta w_j + \gamma w_j^2$ the slope of eq. (4) can be represented by :

$$\frac{(d\chi''_{ij}/dw_j)_{w_j \rightarrow 0}}{(d\chi'_{ij}/dw_j)_{w_j \rightarrow 0}} = \omega\tau_j \quad (5)$$

The eq. (5) represents the ratio of linear coefficients of individual variation of both χ''_{ij} and χ'_{ij} with w_j of a polar solute displayed graphically in Figs. 2 and 3 respectively, τ_j 's estimated from eq. (5) are placed in Table 1 in order to compare them with τ_j 's obtained by direct slope $\chi''_{ij} - \chi'_{ij}$ of Fig. 1 and those of Gopala Krishna's method¹⁰ measured by Pant *et al.*⁵.

The imaginary part χ''_{ij} of $hf \chi_{ij}^*$ is related to w_j of polar solute by¹¹

$$\chi''_{ij} = \frac{N\rho_{ij}\mu_j^2}{27\epsilon_0 M_j k_B T} \left(\frac{\omega\tau_j}{1 + \omega^2\tau_j^2} \right) (\epsilon_{ij} + 2)^2 w_j \quad (6)$$

which on differentiation with respect to w_j and in the limit of $w_j = 0$ yields that

$$\left(\frac{d\chi''_{ij}}{dw_j} \right)_{w_j=0} = \frac{N\rho_{ij}\mu_j^2}{27\epsilon_0 M_j k_B T} \left(\frac{\omega\tau_j}{1 + \omega^2\tau_j^2} \right) (\epsilon_i + 2)^2 \quad (7)$$

From eqs. (5) and (7) one obtains $hf \mu_j$ by

$$\mu_j = \left[\frac{27\epsilon_0 M_j k_B T \beta}{N\rho_i (\epsilon_i + 2)^2 b} \right]^{1/2} \quad (8)$$

M_j = Molecular weight of j -th liquid in Kilogram, ϵ_0 = permittivity of free space = 8.854×10^{-12} Farad metre⁻¹, k_B = Boltzmann constant = 1.38×10^{-23} J mol⁻¹ K⁻¹, T = temperature in absolute scale, $\beta = (d\chi'_{ij}/dw_j)_{w_j \rightarrow 0}$ = linear coefficient of $\chi'_{ij} - w_j$ curves of Fig. 3 at $w_j \rightarrow 0$, N = Avogadro's number = 6.023×10^{23} , ρ_i = density of solvent C_6H_6 , $b = 1/(1 + \omega^2\tau_j^2)$, a dimensionless parameter involved with the estimated τ_j of eq. (5).

Dielectric relaxation is a process of rotation of the polar molecules under hf electric field and it requires an activation energy ΔF_τ , known as free energy of activation to overcome the energy barrier between two equilibrium positions. ΔF_τ is, however, related with estimated τ_j of eq. (5) by the relation¹⁴.

$$\tau_j = \frac{A}{T} \exp(\Delta F_\tau/RT) \quad (9)$$

As $\Delta F_\tau = \Delta H_\tau - T\Delta S_\tau$ so we have

$$\text{or, } \ln(\tau_j T) = \ln A' + \frac{\Delta H_\tau}{R} \frac{1}{T} \quad (10)$$

$$\text{where } A' = A e^{(-\Delta S_\tau/R)} \quad (11)$$

The eq. (10) is a linear equation of $\ln \tau_j T$ against $1/T$ of Fig. 6. The slope and intercept are used to measure the required thermodynamic energy parameters of the molecules as presented in Table 3 in agreement with those of Pant *et al.*⁵.

Results and discussion

The τ_j 's of aromatic polar nitro compounds in solvent C_6H_6 at different experimental temperatures in $^{\circ}C$ under 9.58 Giga Hertz electric field are worked out from the slope of the fitted linear eq. (4) between the variables χ''_{ij} and χ'_{ij} displayed graphically in Fig. 1 with the symbols showing the experimental points. τ_j 's so obtained are compared with τ_j 's estimated from the ratio of linear coefficients of individual variations of both χ''_{ij} and χ'_{ij} with w_j 's shown graphically in Figs. 2 and 3. τ_j 's estimated by both the method are presented in Table 1. The excellent agreement of τ_j 's by both the methods at once indicates the data χ''_{ij} and χ'_{ij} are of low concentrations such that the polar-polar interactions are almost eliminated⁹ at $w_j \rightarrow 0$. The τ_j 's by the latter method²¹ are more reliable. Gopala Krishna's method¹⁰ was employed by Pant *et al.*⁵ to get τ_j 's. They are presented in Table 1. The close agreement between τ_j 's of Pant *et al.*⁵ and estimated τ_j 's of eqs. (4) and (5) at once reflects the basic soundness⁹ of our method to get τ_j in the limit $w_j = 0$. The correlation coefficient and % of error of both $\chi''_{ij} - w_j$ and $\chi'_{ij} - w_j$ curves of Figs. 2 and 3 are given in Table 1 only to show how far they are correlated with w_j 's. It is evident from Table 1 that τ_j 's decrease with temperature. This can be explained on the basis of the fact that at constant temperature, the relaxation time depends upon the energy difference between the activated and normal states. At higher temperature thermal agitation causes an increase in energy loss due to large number of collisions and thereby decreasing the relaxation time^{9,16}. Dipole moments μ_j 's of the polar solutes as estimated from eq. (8) are placed in Table 2 together with linear coefficients β 's of $\chi'_{ij} - w_j$ curves of Fig. 2 and dimensionless parameter b 's involved with τ_j of eq. (5) as seen in Table 2 respectively. They are, however, compared with μ_j 's of Pant *et al.*⁵ and theoretical $\mu_{i,theo}$'s obtained from vector addition of bond moments¹⁷ of the substituted polar groups of the compounds, as seen in the Table 2. The theoretical dipole moment and its orientation as a consequence of known structure of the pertinent nitro-compound is displayed in Fig. 4. The resonance effect thus obtained by solvent benzene compound into an inductive effect operated by the substituent polar groups in the ring is expected to play a prominent role¹⁸ in the measured $hf\mu_j$'s. The disagreement between $hf\mu_j$'s and $\mu_{i,theo}$'s is explained by the influence of hf electric field coupled with inductive and mesomeric moments on the flexible polar groups. $\mu_{i,theo}$'s with reference to Fig. 4 gives a deep insight into the structures of the molecules concerned.

The symmetry and asymmetry of the molecules being a physico-chemical property can well be explained on the basis of $\mu_j - t$ curves of Fig. 5. It is seen that unlike system III all the systems show convex $\mu_j - t$ curves having minimum μ_j 's at lower and higher temperatures due to strong symmetry attained⁸ at those temperatures. The system III shows maximum μ_j 's at lower and higher temperature due to asymmetric shape of the molecule. Physico-chemical properties of the systems can also be explained from the stand point of thermodynamics by estimating the energy parameters ΔH_{τ} , ΔS_{τ} and ΔF_{τ} from the intercept and slope of a fitted linear equation of $\ln \tau_j T$ against $1/T$ shown graphically in Fig. 6 with the experimental points placed on them. They are placed in Table 3 together with those estimated by Pant *et al.*⁵ by using Gopala Krishna's method¹⁰. It is seen that except the first one the other systems are close to each other. Unlike systems II and V all the systems possess negative ΔS_{τ} 's which suggests that configuration involved in dipolar rotation has an activated state which is more ordered than the normal state^{8,19} while the reverse is true for the rest two systems. ΔF_{τ} 's for all the systems are nearly same in magnitude, as the activation is accomplished by the rupture of bond of dipolar groups in the same degrees of freedom^{7,19}. Unlike 2,5-dichloronitrobenzene and 2,5-dibromonitrobenzene all the systems possess $\delta > 0.50$ as seen in Table 3 indicating solvent environment around the solute molecules¹⁵. Moreover, they show higher ΔH_{η} 's than that ΔH_{τ} 's as seen in Table 3. It is due to the fact that ΔH_{η} is involved with both transitional and rotational motion of the molecules. Other systems possess lower values than that of ΔH_{τ} for high value of δ for those systems. Debye factor $\tau_j T / \eta$ and Kalman factor τ_j / η ⁸, being proportional to volume of the rotating unit are carefully estimated and are placed in Table 3. Debye factors are all of the order of 10^6 and Kalman factors although of different orders but found to have constant values for all systems at each temperature, indicating at once the validity of Debye model of dielectric relaxation mechanism for such aromatic polar nitro compounds in C_6H_6 under GHz electric field^{9,13}.

Conclusion :

Our group²¹ have developed a new method based on the complex susceptibility χ''_{ij} in the limit $w_j=0$ to study the structural aspects and physico-chemical properties of the polar nitro liquid compounds 2,5-dichloronitrobenzene, 3,5-dichloronitrobenzene, 2,5-dibromonitrobenzene, 2,4-dinitrochlorobenzene and 3,4-dinitrochlorobenzene in C_6H_6 under GHz electric field at different experimental temperatures. The excellent agreement of τ_j 's estimated by our methods of eqs. (4) and (5) at once establishes the ap-

plicability of the method suggested to get τ_j 's at $w_j \rightarrow 0$ as it eliminates polar-polar interaction²¹ in a given solution. The correlation coefficients r 's and % of errors obtained by careful regression analysis between variables of curves of Figs 2 and 3 show how far the variables χ_{ij} and χ_{ij} are correlated with w_j 's to establish the statistical validity¹⁵ of eq (5). The thermodynamic energy parameters such as ΔH_τ , ΔS_τ and ΔI_τ worked out in terms of temperature variation of τ_j 's are useful and important tools to comment on the physico-chemical properties of dipolar liquid molecules. The theoretical dipole moment μ_{theo} 's and its comparison with measured $lf\mu_j$'s of the eq (8) explore new concept regarding structures of the molecules in addition to inductive, mesomeric and electromeric effects present in them. Almost the constant values of Debye and Kalman factors and the curves satisfied by experimental points in all the figures reflect the validity of the theoretical formulations within the framework of Debye-Smyth model of dielectric relaxation. The significant contribution to study the structural aspects and physico-chemical properties of the polar liquid molecules as sketched in Fig 4 in nonpolar solvent under nearly 10 GHz electric field are thus found to be important to enhance scientific content of the existing knowledge of dielectric relaxation processes.

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